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The Post-Brexit Paradigm: Investigating the Effects of Foreign Direct Investment on Economic Growth in the United Kingdom

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ABSTRACT

In Europe, the United Kingdom is still one of the most sought-after locations for foreign direct investment (FDI). It is generally agreed that FDI benefits nations since it may lead to the development of new sectors, the improvement of existing ones, the distribution of innovative technologies, and the maintenance of healthy economic growth. The Brexit referendum held in June 2016 ultimately made the United Kingdom leave the European Union. As a result, the United Kingdom has seen a steady drop in FDI during the last seven years. Britain's membership in the European Union formally ended on January 31, 2020. The fundamental goal of this research is to illuminate the critical function of FDI in promoting economic growth. In addition, we want to learn how FDI affects GDP growth after Brexit. This study's results corroborate the role of FDI in determining the development path of the British economy following Brexit. There has been a clear drop in UK FDI after Brexit, supporting our theory that FDI plays a major role in determining GDP growth in the post-Brexit era. In addition, Brexit has had a major depressing effect on growth in the British economy. Although FDI does put some downward pressure on the UK economy, the positive impact of capital investment should be noticed. The Brexit vote has diminished the United Kingdom's allure as a prime location for FDI in Europe. Policymakers must reverse this trend and create conditions that attract FDI if the British economy continues growing.

Keywords: FDI; Economic Growth; Brexit; Capital investment; Inflation; External trade; UK.

1. INTRODUCTION

Several economies benefit from the buffering effect of FDI, which helps them weather the inevitable boom-and-bust cycles of the contemporary capitalist economy (Zaman, 2023a). FDI can help most countries develop economically. FDI is defined by Carkovic & Levine (2002) as money from a non-national government or government-owned company invested in a country. FDI often entails the formation or purchase of assets, the distribution of equity, and the launch of for-profit enterprises. In all circumstances, the investor can control the business and acquire access to valuable information, resources, or infrastructure in the target industry. In certain nations (Meng et al., 2023), foreign investors cannot own more than 10% of a company's voting stock. FDI and portfolio investments have different features, yet the terms are interchangeable. Investing in the securities market of a nation from outside the country is known as "foreign portfolio investment." Trading on a foreign stock or bond market falls within this category (Ellington, 2022).

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Differences in geography, geology, technology, politics, and infrastructure all affect how a country's economy and capital develop and grow (Zaman, 2023b,c). This research tries to probe what effect Brexit would have on foreign direct investment in the United Kingdom. FDI is important because it helps developing countries access cutting-edge technologies and creates new jobs. Many factors, some of which vary greatly from country to country, affect capital accumulation and economic development promotion. Therefore, this research examines how Brexit could affect FDI in the British economy. Among the many benefits of FDI for emerging economies is creating new jobs and disseminating game-changing innovations (Easterly, 2006; Talla Fokam et al., 2023). New economic employment, introducing innovative skills and technology, upgrading existing capacities, and promoting steady and continuous growth are just some of the many ways nations benefit from FDI (Acheampong et al., 2023). Economic growth in the host country is boosted by FDI, which attracts foreign capital, promotes the spread of cutting-edge technological know-how, encourages commerce across borders, and helps workers gain valuable management experience. The British stock market is valued at about £1 trillion, attracting more FDI than any other in Europe. The United Kingdom wanted FDI to increase productivity, production, and wages and ranked third in the world regarding FDI receipts, behind only the United States and China. FDI's advantages may be felt both immediately and over time. Multinational corporations outside the UK contribute significantly to the economy (Ali et al., 2022). Foreign-owned companies only comprised 4% of UK businesses in 2018, yet they were responsible for 40% of the country's revenue and employed 4.9 million people. Investors surveyed by Victor et al. 20221 wanted the United Kingdom to improve its FDI incentives, trade agreement access, skilled immigration policy, R&D funding, and workforce development. The United Kingdom's ability to attract foreign investment has been a key factor in the country's sustained outperformance relative to other economies regarding productivity growth, wage increases, and the spread of new ideas and techniques. However, FDI has dropped since the Brexit decision, and the United Kingdom is no longer in the lead compared to its competitors. Between 2017 and 2021, the United Kingdom had the lowest average FDI as a percentage of GDP. Before Brexit, the United Kingdom had the highest FDI openness among advanced economies, with a trade-to-GDP ratio on par with its competitors. However, Britain's trade openness for FDI is the lowest in the European Union after Brexit. After Brexit, UK foreign direct investment growth lags behind other major countries in the Pacific. The extent to which this drop in trade and FDI harms the British economy depends on the measures taken by the government. Limiting domestic company competitiveness and innovation and reducing trade openness do both. A lack of FDI and a homogeneous workforce hampers productivity development. Because of Brexit, the United Kingdom will play a smaller role in the global economy; thus, changes will need to be made to soften the blow (Posen & Rengifo-Keller, 2022).

Most economists believe Britain's choice to exit the European Union would hurt the economy in the long-run (Parker, 2018). Economists polled before the 2016 vote forecast that the United Kingdom's per capita income will fall due to Brexit. Forecasts for GDP drop in 2019 varied from 1.5% to 4%. In addition, between 1% and 10% yearly pay reductions in the UK were predicted due to Brexit (Sampson, 2017). The degree to which Brexit would be a "hard" or "soft" departure significantly impacted these projections. The British government commissioned a study in January 2018 that predicted a 2-8% yearly drop in economic growth after Brexit, depending on the withdrawal option selected. This reduction was predicted to last for at least 15 years. Leaving the EU, as predicted by the vast majority of experts, would be disastrous for the British economy. The University of Cambridge economists have predicted that tariffs on British exports to the EU would range from 1% to 10% when the UK leaves the EU (Corsetti et al., 2022). According to the results of this research (Chen et al., 2017), the United Kingdom is particularly susceptible to the effects of Brexit. Furthermore, a 2017 study predicts that tighter immigration limits after Brexit would hurt the UK economy and GDP while only slightly boosting salaries in the low-skill service sector. Companies' site selections and investment preferences are affected by several variables. Businesses often expand into more populous and profitable regions to better serve their clientele. The United Kingdom is still desirable for FDI despite its membership in the European Union because of its strong legal system, flexible labour markets, and highly educated workforce. However, joining the EU may increase FDI because of lower trade and investment costs. This research aims better to comprehend the dynamics between GDP expansion and FDI. This study aims to make conclusions about this connection in the wake of Brexit by evaluating observable data.

The examination of UK FDI trends through time is shown in Figure 1. It shows that FDI in the UK has been falling since 2016. This decline may be traced back to the June 23, 2016, Brexit vote. The referendum results indicated that 51.9% preferred withdrawing from the European Union. The governing party then decided to follow through with the referendum's implementation despite lacking legitimacy. FDI in the United Kingdom has fallen the fastest since the EU vote, which began in 2016.

Figure 1: FDI in the UK

Source: Author's estimate based on the given dataset.

Since the Brexit vote, foreign investment projects scheduled to launch in the UK have decreased by 16–20%. FDI in the services sector may be as much as 25% lower than it would have been if the UK had remained in the EU. Since the quantity of FDI, a project obtains may be affected by the degree of uncertainty around it (Resmini, 2000; Singh & Jun, 1995). Investment is still happening in the UK at a far lower rate than before. Due to the Brexit decision, many high-paying jobs in these industries are in peril. Therefore, the present uncertainties have had a major impact on FDI in the UK. Foreign direct investment in the UK is seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2: FDI after Brexit in the UK

Source: Author's estimate based on the given dataset.

On January 31, 2020, the United Kingdom will officially leave the European Union. Figure 2 shows how FDI in the UK fell following Brexit. Even though conducting business inside the European Union may entail substantial expenses, the United Kingdom is appealing to multinational firms as an export destination due to its complete inclusion into the Single Market. Because of this, FDI has decreased since Brexit. Coordinating between a parent company and its provincial branches may be expensive, and multinational companies' supply chains are naturally more complicated. Problems will be more work once the United Kingdom quits the European Union. It may be easier to migrate personnel inside an organization if migration standards are made more stringent and different charges and limitations are placed on different parts. However, FDI is likely to be hampered by the unknown nature of trade arrangements between the UK and the EU.

1.1. Problem statement

FDI is money a company or group headquartered in one country spends to do business in another. When foreign entities buy stock on a country's stock market, this is an example of portfolio flows, which is quite different. FDI often results in the investor having significant influence and control over the target company. Compared to a closed economy with strict restrictions, an open economy with a qualified workforce and strong development prospects is more likely to attract FDI (Tanweer et al., 2023). Conflicting results have emerged from the available empirical research on the effect of FDI on GDP expansion. However, there is a prevailing paradigm in the area of international development that the majority of research follows. FDI, alone or in conjunction with other variables, has been linked favorably to economic growth in several country-specific studies. Wang (2009) suggests considering FDI as a whole rather than breaking it down by industry. However, Edison et al. (2002) showed that it is difficult to generalize across studies owing to changes in research design, study demographics, sample lengths, data sources, and estimating procedures. Wang (2009) is quite accurate in pointing out the divide of opinion on this issue. As a result, it is essential to examine how Brexit can affect the bearing of FDI on the development of the British economy. Novel data and consideration of Brexit's special conditions, largely ignored by previous researchers, form the basis of this study.

1.2. Rational of the Study

FDI is universally acknowledged as an important contributor to economic development and job creation. It is essential for global value chains because it promotes productivity growth, effective capital allocation, and international economic integration. It is a safe way to transfer money across borders while fostering innovation, commerce, and the spread of new technologies. When a citizen or permanent resident of one nation (the direct investor) invests in a firm headquartered in another economy (the direct investment entity), they create a long-term, direct relationship between the two economies. A direct investor chooses to work with a company because he or she hopes to create a long-term strategic partnership with the business and exert a strong influence over its day-to-day operations. Bruno et al. (2017) found that EU membership increased average FDI by 28%. This estimate is consistent with findings from other similar research. Therefore, it is predicted that if the United Kingdom were to exit the European Union and the Single Market, FDI would dramatically decrease. The United Kingdom's allure as an investment destination would decrease if its economic linkages with the European Union were restricted and net migration was reduced. Previous empirical data has shown that the United Kingdom profited greatly from FDI from other EU member states when it joined the union. Theoretical forecasts of a drop in FDI after Britain's exit from the European Union are borne out by the available data. Previous research often used gravity or panel data models to assess the decline in FDI. However, only a few articles used Poisson models using panel data. However, previous studies have shown that FDI would likely decrease after Brexit. Both Campos & Coricelli (2015) and Ebell & Warren (2016) agree that the British economy would suffer due to the country's decision to leave the European Union. However, a comprehensive analysis of how FDI programmes affect employment is lacking. Considering the continued strength and stability of the British pound, the reputation for high-quality products, and the status as a major global commercial and financial centre, it is crucial to analyse how FDI influences economic growth in the United Kingdom after Brexit.

1.3. Research Gap, Objectives, Questions, and Study's Significance

The link between FDI and economic expansion has been the subject of much research. However, there is no evidence of the effect of FDI on GDP growth in the wake of Brexit (the United Kingdom's departure from the European Union). Given FDI's importance to GDP growth, this research tries to analyze how it has changed after Brexit. This research aims to examine the role that FDI had in driving economic expansion in the United Kingdom both before and after the Brexit vote. The following issues will be explored in order to accomplish the study's goals:

RQ1: What is the relationship between FDI and Economic Growth in the UK?

RQ2: How does FDI impact economic growth after Brexit?

This research examines how FDI has helped the British economy grow after the Brexit vote. The study's conclusions will help enhance the country's regulatory structure and encourage more foreign direct investment. It also seeks to educate the British people on why FDI is important for the country's economy. The completion of a master's degree programme in accounting and finance will benefit from this study as well. Additionally, this study intends to contribute to creating standardized metrics for analyzing the impacts of FDI on economic growth by providing a platform for comparing its results with other studies.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

A substantial body of literature is devoted to studying economic growth because of the widespread interest in the issue among economists. Analyzing data from several researches is required to determine whether or not FDI helps drive economic expansion. We want to ascertain the effect of FDI on economic growth by reviewing relevant microeconomic research. Spickernell (2014) investigates the impact of FDI on developing countries. The research emphasizes the importance of FDI in theories of economic growth's beginnings and dynamics. FDI is generally considered critical to host countries' economic health. It is essential for

spreading technology in developing countries because it promotes economic development like private domestic investment. The host economy also benefits from the spillover effects of FDI, including increased human capital and more jobs. Investment companies often create regional partnerships to access new management talent. Aswathappa et al. (2010) calculated that FDI brought in over 300 billion pounds in 2000. Long-term infrastructure projects are a typical beneficiary of FDI, especially in developed nations. This category of endeavors includes new enterprises, infrastructure construction, and energy generation. Numerous academics, notably Alfaro et al. (2004) and Hermes & Lensink (2008), have analyzed the effects of FDI on advanced economies. All applicable domestic rules were followed throughout their investigation. Market success may depend on several elements, including the market's size and structure, the financial system's breadth, the number of available jobs, and the ease with which credit may be obtained. According to the study, FDI and economic development are more probable in countries with strong government control and efficient financial systems. Companies in the investment industry depend on readily available financial resources like loans, which can only exist in a healthy economic climate. Deregulation to encourage foreign direct investment has far-reaching effects on economies. In order to successfully attract FDI, host governments must offer a stable financial environment for local and foreign businesses. Attracting FDI requires several other variables, including institutional backing, strong macroeconomics, qualified labour, and a functioning infrastructure.

FDI may benefit host economies primarily via two channels: introducing new technology and generating skilled labor. Spillovers help spread new technologies when home-based businesses obtain cutting-edge tools without worrying about patent infringement. Companies that receive investments from others often benefit from the transfer of expertise through improved management techniques and more streamlined operations. However, it might be difficult for host nations to fully realize the advantages of FDI depending on their unique development indices, such as education and vital infrastructure. Stehrer & Woerz (2009) performed an empirical study to determine whether FDI contributed to GDP growth. To perform their empirical study, the researchers look at data from host nations over twenty years. The results demonstrate that FDI promotes economic growth by contributing to higher production and exports. Consistent with the findings of Li & Liu (2005) and Stehrer & Woerz (2009), it has been shown that a 10% increase in FDI results in a 1.2% rise in production. The impact of foreign direct investment on the GDP growth of 84 nations is analyzed here. The findings prove that FDI boosts economic development through increasing stock capital. Notably, 84 nations, including both high- and low-income countries, are used to investigate the effects of FDI. Vu et al. (2009) emphasize the growth-inducing impacts of FDI, finding that a comparable 10% rise in FDI levels results in a 4.1% increase in economic expansion in high-income and low-income nations.

Several authors, including Santos (2023) and Amara et al. (2023), have stressed the importance of FDI in fostering economic expansion. It helps economies expand because it facilitates the sharing of knowledge and the development of new goods and technologies. According to Anakpo et al. (2023), advanced economies may benefit from FDI to varying degrees depending on their access to and use of cutting-edge technology. By adopting and implementing new technology, industrialized countries may simplify their exports and imports. FDI is good for host economies because of the spillover effects, which may be technological transfer via imitation, learning from more advanced foreign enterprises, competition, links, and training. Foreign enterprises with sophisticated technology create competitive spillovers, compelling domestic firms to use cutting-edge methods. Organizational efforts to train workers also help raise overall skill levels. According to Liu (2008), nations that took part in studies examining the correlation between FDI and GDP had good results. Using data from 69 nations over several periods, Borensztein et al. (1998) investigate the connection between FDI and GDP. The research used cross-country regression methods to suggest that, under some conditions, FDI may boost GDP growth. The host country should implement measures to guarantee a steady supply of skilled people to ensure high-quality output. FDI is a key factor in the spread of new technologies since it has been shown to have a greater effect on GDP growth than local investment. FDI is believed to boost economic development by increasing the host country's productivity by importing advanced management techniques, specialist knowledge, and cutting-edge tools. Foreign investors are more likely to put money into a nation that has attracted a lot of FDI. It helps refill the host country's economy. According to Dunning (2012), FDI may serve as either an input to or an output from domestic investment. Domestic investment benefits from the host country's access to funding made possible by FDI. Finance for FDI projects often comes from the host country's currency; therefore, expanding access to credit in that market is essential. Ping et al. (2019) conducted an empirical investigation of the detrimental impacts of FDI on the country of destination. Foreign enterprises entering the local market may increase competition, which can increase production efficiency, output, and investment in material resources. This can boost exports by increasing the quality of local products. Another source of positive externalities is the interaction between international and domestic corporations, which promotes the exchange of new ideas and technological advances. Finally, training programmes help improve employees' abilities in all areas of their work lives, from hands-on to management. When foreign investors in a country embrace cutting-edge technology that local enterprises quickly reproduce, the host country benefits from positive externalities.

Like "Grexit," which describes Greece's decision to quit the Eurozone, "BREXIT" refers to "Britain's Exit from the EU. The divorce between the United Kingdom and the European Union is final. Now that the United Kingdom has left the European Union, it is no longer bound by EU law and cannot participate in the Single Market or the Customs Union. The British government must lay out the prerequisites for holding a referendum on Britain's departure from the European Union. The costs and advantages of EU membership financially and the freedom of movement for EU personnel were major points of contention leading up to the referendum. Tax money now going to the EU may be better used at home, proponents of Britain's secession from the EU said (Till & Panu, 2016). Proponents of leaving the EU said that staying in would increase competition in the job market, unemployment, and government expenditure. They said Britain would profit from leaving the EU, reinvesting in the economy, and restricting the employment rights of EU nationals, notwithstanding the probable negative effects on the economy. Article 50 of the Treaty on the European Union must be invoked when a member state intends to quit the EU. With this clause, any EU member state may legally resign its membership. When a member state initiates the procedure for leaving the EU, discussions begin to settle the terms of departure and the status of the country's future relationship with the EU. Voters in the United Kingdom decided to leave the European Union officially on March 29, 2017, after a referendum conducted on June 23, 2016. Until the official departure date of February 1, 2020, the terms of the agreement negotiated to secure a peaceful exit and protect the UK's legal obligations will remain in effect. The transition period started on February 1, 2020, and the UK remained in the EU until December. Starting on January 1, 2021, the "Trade and Cooperation Agreement" will serve as the legislative framework for EU-UK ties. The people of the European Union and the United Kingdom will gain a great deal from this landmark agreement. The four pillars of the Internal Market—free movement of money (including FDI), people, services, and goods—are influenced by economic integration. Free movement of capital, trade in products and services, labour mobility, and passporting rules have made the United Kingdom attractive for FDI inside Europe, as stated by Ebell & Wareen (2016). Increased exports to Central and Eastern Europe (CEE) nations, which do not have a single external tariff with the EU, have contributed to the continued rise of British FDI since entering the EU. Initiated in the late 1980s, the Single Market Programme worked to lower domestic hurdles to external investment and commerce. Compared to partnerships with non-EU nations, those with EU members saw a 28% rise in foreign direct investment stockpiles. According to Campos & Coricelli (2015), the increase in FDI of 25–30% in bilateral flows between 1986 and 2015 may be attributed to the United Kingdom's participation in the European Union. These authors used various economic models and found that bilateral FDI flows increased by an average of 28%.

Bloom et al. (2012) found that higher levels of FDI in the UK correlate with higher productivity due to better management practices and more advanced technologies. Companies at home that get FDI and succeed might anticipate similar success. Alfaro et al. (2004) show that the country's well-developed financial industry bolsters FDI's effect on the UK economy. Increased FDI flows due to EU admission resulted in a 2.25% boost in GDP, as determined by Pain and Young's (2004) examination of a macroeconomic model of the British economy that included endogenous monetary and fiscal policy. Nevertheless, Brexit might undermine the gains from monetary union via FDI. The investment and economic environment in the United Kingdom might change due to Brexit, and the degree to which individual nations have autonomy over their affairs is another possible consequence. A drop in FDI in the economy after Brexit might have far-reaching consequences. Brexit will likely affect the legal framework and the ease of establishment for EU member states in the UK. The United Kingdom may also lose access to EU member states' protective measures after Brexit (Barret et al., 2015). Research commissioned by the UK Treasury indicated that post-Brexit real income would fall by 10%. The UK Treasury has run trade simulations and FDI evaluations to gauge the short-term economic impact of possibly limited access to the EU single market. The potential economic consequences of higher FDI barriers imposed on the UK by the EU27 after March 2019 are explored in studies by Francois & Manchin (2013) on the effects of the Transatlantic Trade and Investment Partnership (TTIP) on EU member countries and McGrattan & Waddle (2020) on the effects of Brexit on FDI and production structure. The planned removal of further transatlantic obstacles is expected to result in an 11% increase in employment for US firms operating in the EU28. BEA estimates place US FDI in the EU28 at about 3% of GDP. The employment implications of lowering barriers to FDI are projected to raise GDP growth by 0.33 percentage points. The exact ramifications for production and employment in the EU27 due to a reduction in British FDI in the EU will depend on the severity of limits imposed by the EU27 after March 2019. Only by considering them can the effect of Brexit on the UK's FDI environment be evaluated. FDI is important since it influences multinational enterprises' competitiveness and trade costs because of trade barriers and distance. If trade barriers are raised, FDI will rise due to increased international transportation costs. London's status as a financial services hub may be threatened if businesses decide to move output elsewhere in the EU due to Brexit (Mansfield, 2014). Large transition expenses are possible for businesses with a major presence in the EU in the UK. The United Kingdom must improve its business environment and taxation framework to face increasing competition after Brexit. Reducing social regulations and taxes may partly restore competitiveness, which may deteriorate due to Brexit. The European Union faces serious threats if the United Kingdom follows Ireland's lead and agrees to all the conditions of EU membership.

When companies are based in various countries, optimizing their global supply chains might be another factor that encourages foreign direct investment. British companies may need help, such as increased trade costs and prolonged processing times if they decide to move their operations to another EU member state. Furthermore, European Union companies may consider cutting the United Kingdom out of their worldwide supply chains. The additional trade barriers established after Brexit might cause enterprises outside of Europe to reevaluate the United Kingdom as their most important trading partner. Between 2005 and 2014, Barret et al. (2015) analyzed the emergence of new foreign affiliates in EU member states. There is a 12.7% chance that a foreign parent firm will open a shop in the UK. This probability drops to 2.9% if access to the British market is cut in half. Some banks' choice to move operations outside of the UK is seen as contributing to the emigration of capital. Nissan and Toyota made public announcements of factory closures and relocations in 2016. Academics like Driffield & Karoglou (2019) recognize the considerable uncertainty of the international system and hence abstain from offering a precise numerical assessment of the effect of Brexit on FDI. Brexit has a detrimental impact on FDI in the UK, according to their analysis employing a Markov regime-switching structural vector-autoregression. They advocated for loosening regulations on the job market, trading more with nations that had cheaper labour, and reducing worker rights. One must also consider how Brexit would affect nations where the United Kingdom has substantial assets. According to Barrett et al. (2015), if FDI levels between Ireland and the UK were to fall, it would harm Ireland's GDP growth and might cause a decline in British FDI projects in Ireland. Recent studies of EU citizens' effects on FDI inflows and outflows were summarized by Dhingra et al. (2016). FDI flows between 34 OECD nations were used in the gravity regressions done by Bruno et al. (2017), with EU membership used as an independent variable. Campos & Coricelli (2015) expected a 22% drop in FDI, and their results matched that prediction. In the baseline scenario, the model predicts that FDI in the UK would rise rather than fall due to Brexit measures implemented in other countries. To predict the effects of rising trade costs after Brexit, Steinberg (2019) used a dynamic model. He foresaw a gradual reduction in UK GDP, with output decreasing by 0.4% to 1.1% from pre-Brexit levels. More severe consequences are shown in the baseline scenario, where the UK and the EU each increase trade and FDI costs for each other, leading to a decline in production of over 1% on average in the first decade after the transition and ultimately surpassing 3%. Both FDI inflows and outflows are affected by price increases, but the former is more so than the latter in a stagnating economy. Research disproves the statements made by Arkolakis et al. (2018), which state that human labour is the sole productive component in single-product businesses. You discovered, instead, that worldwide expenditures on technological capital would be most affected by the result of Brexit. What is more, unlike Arkolakis, whose attention was restricted to the industrial sector, the study approach has broad implications for the economy as a whole.

3. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

3.1. Dependency Theory

The Dependency Theory is a point of view on the state of developing, non-industrialized countries that was created by Hills (1994). It contradicts conventional wisdom by spotlighting the impact of global political, economic, and cultural factors on domestic development policies and practices. The Dependency Theory challenges the idea that all civilizations progress along the same trajectory by positing, instead, that growing countries have distinctive traits and institutional systems. It considers these countries less capable competitors in the global market than industrialized countries. According to the Dependency Theory (Irogbe, 2005), Richer countries purposefully hold poorer countries in a submissive position. Economic sanctions, trade restrictions, and structural adjustment programmes in return for loans from international organizations like the IMF and World Bank are used to attain this goal. There are structural, functional, and purposeful theories for reliance, all of which Frank (1974) explored. He claims the theory needs to address the rising gap between the urban core and rural periphery due to globalization and is of little use to those who desire to disrupt the system. According to the Dependency Theory, developed countries use FDI to exert power over their less-developed counterparts. This view holds that FDI harms developing nations because multinational businesses prefer to abuse economic possibilities for their gain rather than sharing the spoils fairly with the countries that welcome them. Asongu et al. (2018) point out that this may cause domestic economic instability and prevent people in developing nations from benefiting from overseas investment.

3.2. Classical Theory

According to Harrod and Domar's classical growth theory (Kanayo, 2013), increased capital utilization or accumulation is the key factor in economic expansion. This idea emerged in the 1930s and 1940s to back up Keynesian economics. The Harrod-Domar model predicts a negative relationship between investment and production. To calculate marginal capital productivity, the model multiplies the investment rate by the growth rate, which is assumed to be constant. According to the Harrod-Domar model, governments may significantly boost economic growth by enacting policies that affect investment (Rumawir, 2019). Governments may influence investor choices by offering incentives like tax cuts and public sector initiatives. The model provides an optimistic assessment of politics' role in fostering economic expansion. However, sceptics point to the model's assumptions of constant

marginal capital productivity and a non-endogenous explanation of the investment ratio. The traditional growth hypothesis suggests that the host nation will profit from FDI. It boosts economic development in both home and host countries (Obinger et al., 2013). Long-term, FDI helps the host country because it increases commerce, transfers managerial expertise, spreads technology, and creates more competition.

3.3. *The internalization Theory and the Electric Paradigm of Dunning*

The internalization hypothesis explains why and how MNCs engage in FDI and what drives them to do so. This hypothesis suggests that eradicating local competition and the benefits to businesses from entering a new line of business are the primary motivators of FDI (Denisia, 2010). How MNCs might optimize their internal organizational structure to reap specific advantages in international markets is the subject of the internalization hypothesis (Rugman, 2010). Knowledge, components, and raw materials may more easily move across manufacturing sites within an organization thanks to the intermediation products emphasized by the idea. According to the internalization idea, corporations should avoid disclosing their confidential information to other companies, preferring to keep it under wraps. Firms may keep their competitive edge and reap the benefits of their expertise by establishing an internal knowledge market. According to Markusen (1995), internal information exchange contributes to developing bigger, more successful companies worldwide. As state-of-the-art technologies and inventions are refined, the company's scientists and engineers share their findings with their peers worldwide, allowing the international enterprise to grow and improve from within. The internalization theory is often linked to the O-L-I framework. The letter "O" represents the firm's ownership advantages, which are advantages the business has because it owns certain assets or skills. The letter "L" represents the benefits of a market's or a resource's location. In this context, "I" stands for "internalization," which describes a company's choice to handle a certain task in-house instead of outsourcing it to a third party. Firms may increase their chances of success by combining ownership advantages, geographical advantages, and internalization to capitalize on existing strengths and enter new markets.

FDI may be studied in relation to GDP, employment, productivity, technology transfer, and other pertinent indices of economic development by considering FDI as an independent variable and economic growth as a dependent variable. The study's theoretical underpinnings are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Conceptual Model

Source: Author's extract.

Empirical studies examining the connection between FDI and economic development have been conducted based on theoretical frameworks like the neoclassical and endogenous growth models. While more research is needed to pin down the specifics of this connection, there is much evidence from macroeconomics to suggest that FDI has a large impact on the economy.

The following hypotheses were developed for the research based on this information:

H1: FDI has a significant impact on Economic Growth.

When economies are integrated, there are fewer barriers to the free flow of commodities, services, labour, and capital. The United Kingdom has become a prime location for FDI in Europe due to several reasons, including the ease with which products and services can be purchased, the stability of the currency, and the government's pro-trade stance. FDI in the United Kingdom rose when it joined the European Union. According to traditional economic theory, the host nation may reap the advantages of FDI by gaining access to the investor's knowledge, expertise, and resources. The following hypothesis was developed based on the prior examination:

H2: FDI significantly impacts the economic growth of the UK in the aftermath of Brexit.

The impact of FDI on national economies has been studied extensively. Some studies have shown positive results, while others have shown negative effects, and this variation seems to be attributable to the particular factors examined in the estimates, such as the political, economic, and technical characteristics of recipient countries.

4. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study's analysis used information from the World Investment Report and the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development. Dates from each year between 2012 and 2021 are used in the analysis. The statistical method of choice for this study is regression analysis. As a measure of the economy's health, GDP growth will be the focus of this study's analysis. Instead, FDI in the host nation is the research question. The data utilized in this analysis were publicly accessible and were not created specifically for this research. The ease with which secondary data may be collected makes time series analysis a powerful tool for answering various research topics.

The data set was subjected to the Augmented Dickey-Fuller unit-root test and the Philips-Perron unit-root test, both considered stationary tests. Time series analysis relies heavily on stationarity. Data analysis was performed using the VECM (Vector Error Correction Model). Co-integrated VAR (Vector Autoregressive) models include VECM, a subtype. The differenced variables are included in a VAR model with an error correction term based on the known (estimated) co-integrating relationship. The lag order of the VAR model is $p - 1$. Variables that have one or more co-integrating vectors may be estimated using VECM.

Time series variables must be stationary for the VAR model to be estimated. However, according to standard economic theory, there should be no variations in the amounts of economic variables since they are all connected in equilibrium. Co-integration describes this dynamic well. Econometric models like VECMs have been created to take into account these interconnections. More accurate findings may be obtained from empirical investigations when VECMs are used since they consider short-term changes in the variables and departures from equilibrium. The theory and literature inform the suggested lag period for defining a VECM. A typical VECM model is written as follows:

$$\Delta Y_t = a_1 + a_2 ec(t-1) + a_3 \Delta Y(t-1) + a_4 \Delta X(t-1) + \epsilon_t \quad (1)$$

The rate of convergence to equilibrium is quantified by the coefficient of the error correction term ($ec(t-1)$) in the dynamic model estimate of the VECM. To account for both the long-term and short-term associations and the combined effect of these factors, VECM models include all variables, both endogenous (Y) and exogenous (X). The coefficients of the differenced variables capture the immediate impacts. ON THE OTHER HAND, the VECM variable's coefficient shows whether or not the variables' past values affect their present ones. Coefficients of the error correction term provide a quantitative measure of the rate at which all variables settle into a steady state, with greater coefficients suggesting more substantial long-term effects. Cross-panel data approaches are one example of the many modern statistical methods that have emerged in recent years (Zaman, 2023d). The primary focus of this approach is on how diverse international cross-sectional regressors affect a country-specific dependent variable. Furthermore, using CiteScore rank may help gauge the quality of academic work (Zaman, 2023e).

This research analyses time series data for the United Kingdom over ten years (2012-2022) to measure how much FDI contributes to GDP growth. Another goal of this study is to find and evaluate the most important aspects of determining whether foreign direct investment has a good or negative impact. Due to a surplus of labour in all UK economies included in the sample, the explanatory variable of labour was omitted from the study. Given the lag period between FDI and economic development, the delayed benefits of foreign direct investment are explored. The literature may help you figure out how many delays are ideal. Including delayed FDI also helps address economic growth's effect on FDI.

One empirical model is used to evaluate FDI's general effect on GDP growth, while the other is used to examine FDI's unique effect on GDP growth in the wake of Brexit. These types of models are employed:

$$\text{Model 1: } Y_{gt} = b_0 + b_f * FDI_{t-m} + b_k * K_{t-m} + b_p * P_t + b_e * ET_t + b_c * CON_t + \epsilon \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Model 2: } Y_{gt} = b_0 + b_f * FDI_{t-m} * \text{Period} + b_f * FDI_{t-m} + b_p * \text{Period} + b_k * K_{t-m} + b_p * P_t + b_e * ET_t + b_c * CON_t + \epsilon \quad (3)$$

The models' coefficients b_r ($r = 0/f/k/p/e/c$) characterize the varied effects of each independent variable on the regressed one. The models also include the dummy variables Period, K for capital investment and formation, P for inflation, ET for external trade, CON for consumption, and for the error term, where t is the period, m is the time lag ($m = 1, 2, 3, \dots$), Y_g is economic growth, FDI is total FDI inflow, and so on. The values for the variables are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Measurement of Variables

Variables	Proxies	Measurement	Authors
Dependent Variable			
Economic Growth	GDP	Growth of GDP	(Trinh, 2017)
Independent Variables			
FDI	FDI	Net FDI inflow (% of GDP)	(Iamsiraroj, 2016)
Dummy Variable	Period	1 after Brexit, or 0 otherwise	(Donthu et al, 2020)
Control Variables			
Capital Investment	K	Gross Domestic Capital Formation	(Su & Liu, 2016)
Inflation	P	GDP deflator	Ascari & Sbordone (2014)
External Trade	ET	total export/total import	(Azeez, 2014)
Consumption	CON	Final Consumption Expenditure (% GDP)	(Rehman, 2016)

Source: Author's construct.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The descriptive statistics of the primary variables used in this research are shown in Table 2 and are based on financial data from 2012 to 2021. The GDP averages 1.32%, with a standard deviation of 4.69%. This suggests that GDP growth in the UK was relatively weak throughout the period under study.

Table 2: Descriptive Analysis

Variables	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
GDP	1.327	4.693	-11.031	7.525
Period	.2	.422	0	1
FDI	2.493	3.65	-.871	12.032
FDI*Period	.187	.407	0	1.148
K	17.573	.815	15.878	18.35
P	1.946	1.517	.369	5.933
ET	60.429	2.816	56.67	64.13
CON	83.781	.946	82.385	85.262

Source: Author's estimate.

The average level of FDI is 2.49%, with a standard variation of only 0.21%. However, the average FDI percentage dropped to 0.187 following Brexit, suggesting a significant effect on FDI inflows to the UK. Capital investment in the UK averages 17.57%, whereas inflation runs at 1.94% on average and 5.93% at its highest. The UK economy seems to be experiencing considerable inflation according to these numbers. The average percentage of GDP accounted for by exports and imports is 60.42%, with a low of 56.677. This exemplifies the effect on the sum of UK exports and imports. The standard deviation of the consumption value is 0.946, while the mean is \$83.7. This is indicative of rising discretionary spending in the British economy.

The coefficients of correlation between the different variables are shown in Table 3. A negative association between the period and GDP suggests that economic output often falls as the period passes. A positive link between FDI and GDP suggests that FDI contributes to economic expansion. However, FDI negatively affects GDP after Brexit, indicating a different relationship between FDI and GDP in the post-Brexit era.

Table 3: Correlation Matrix

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)
(1) GDP	1							
(2) Period	-0.346	1						
(3) FDI	0.076	-0.225	1					
(4) FDI*Period	-0.565	0.969	-0.211	1				
(5) K	0.239	0.065	0.109	0.003	1			
(6) P	-0.965	0.419	-0.029	0.619	-0.173	1		
(7) ET	0.029	-0.568	-0.159	-0.521	0.005	0.033	1	
(8) CON	0.319	-0.655	0.137	-0.662	-0.702	-0.384	0.183	1

Source: Author's estimate.

GDP growth is positively correlated with increases in capital investment. There is an inverse link between inflation and GDP, as seen by inflation's negative correlation with GDP. The positive association between GDP and foreign trade and consumption suggests that rising levels of both are linked to a more prosperous economy. A unit root test ensured that the information was consistent and trustworthy. The data were tested for stationarity using the ADF and Phillips-Perron unit root tests, yielding the same conclusion. Using the ADF unit root test, it is standard practice to test for unit roots in time series data. The results of a unit root test for the ADF are shown in Table 4 for the initial difference level. The significance thresholds at which the null hypothesis of nonstationary is tested are 1%, 5%, and 10%.

Table 4: Unit Root Estimates

Augment Dickey-Fuller								
Constant	GDP	Period	FDI	FDI*Period	K	P	ET	CON
Z-statistics	-6.27	-2.646	-1.672	-3.628	-2.681	-4.936	-1.849	-2.985
Time Trend include	GDP	Period	FDI	FDI*Period	K	P	ET	CON
Z-statistics	-8.16	-3.667	-2.123	-4.533	-6.224	-4.967	-1.680	-4.688
P-value	0.0000	0.0246	0.5330	0.0013	0.0000	0.0009	0.7579	0.0007
Phillips-Perron								
Constant	GDP	Period	FDI	FDI*Period	K	P	ET	CON
Z-statistics	-6.137	-2.646	-1.635	-3.628	-2.667	-5.272	-1.853	-2.983
Time Trend include	GDP	Period	FDI	FDI*Period	K	P	ET	CON
Z-statistics	-9.257	-3.833	-2.037	-4.826	-8.739	-8.443	-1.647	-7.453
P-value	0.0000	0.0150	0.587	0.0004	0.0000	0.0000	0.7743	0.0000

Source: Author's estimate.

The data in Table 4 shows that the series could be more stable at this level. After data differentiation, however, all series become stable at the 10%, 5%, and 1% significance levels, as shown by the ADF test. This indicates that the variables' initial differences are steady. The results of the ADF test show that all series of variables are first-order integrated series. The Phillips-Perron unit root test was used with the ADF approach to verify the ADF's findings. The estimation of the regression for Model-1 is shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Relationship between FDI and the UK Economic Growth

Variables	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
_ce1 (L)	-1.809	2.498	-0.72	.469	-6.704	3.086	
GDP (LD)	.194	2.482	0.08	.938	-4.671	5.059	
FDI (LD)	-.286	.547	-0.52	.601	-1.359	.786	
Constant	-1.647	2.18	-0.76	.45	-5.919	2.626	
_ce1 (L)	5.454	1.13	4.83	0	3.239	7.669	***
GDP (LD)	-5.383	1.123	-4.79	0	-7.584	-3.182	***
FDI (LD)	.551	.248	2.22	.026	.065	1.036	**
Constant	-.546	.986	-0.55	.58	-2.479	1.387	
Statistical Tests							
Mean dependent var	0.234		SD dependent var		0.448		
Number of obs	8.000						

Source: Author's estimate. *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05.

Model 1, using the VECM to conduct the unit root test, shows that lower levels of FDI harm GDP growth in the UK at the 1% level of statistical significance. Our findings support the idea that FDI is a key factor in fostering economic expansion. Several variables contribute to the negative effect of less FDI on GDP growth. First, FDI inflows bring in foreign money that may be put to work in the economy's productive sectors. Increased output, new employment opportunities, and technical progress are all pushed forward by this investment (Saha, 2023) to fuel economic expansion. Because of this, less foreign money is available for investment and economic growth as FDI falls (Wang et al., 2023). Second, a significant aspect of FDI is the transfer of know-how, expertise, and technology from the home nation to the investor. Increased production and economic growth result from increased competitiveness

and productivity in home industries thanks to this transfer. Reduced FDI may harm economic development and productivity since it reduces the flow of new ideas and practices into the economy (Chishti, 2023) and the number of people exposed to them. In addition, FDI is often linked to elevated trade activity. If foreign investors set up factories in the host nation, exports of locally made items might rise. Overseas investment might also increase imports since overseas businesses may need to source inputs and raw materials from outside (Chiriluş & Costea, 2023) to operate. A drop in FDI can potentially disrupt trade connections, which might slow economic growth. Decreased FDI has a detrimental effect on GDP growth, illustrating the importance of FDI as a motor for economic growth. Capital accumulation, technological diffusion, and greater commerce are all important for long-term economic development, and the results highlight the need for policies and initiatives to attract and maintain FDI. After Brexit, FDI and GDP are compared in Table 6.

Table 6: Relationship between FDI and Economic Growth Before and After BREXIT

Variables	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
GDP	8.77	2.804	3.13	.002	3.274	14.266	***
Constant	.13	1.834	0.07	.944	-3.464	3.724	
Period	-.319	.137	-2.33	.02	-.587	-.051	**
Constant	.131	.09	1.46	.144	-.045	.306	
FDI	-1.111	2.685	-0.41	.679	-6.373	4.152	
Constant	-.043	1.756	-0.02	.981	-3.484	3.399	
FDI*Period	-.479	.146	-3.28	.001	-.765	-.192	***
Constant	.11	.096	1.15	.25	-.077	.297	
K	.531	.277	1.92	.055	-.011	1.074	*
Constant	.213	.181	1.18	.239	-.142	.568	
P	-2.652	.902	-2.94	.003	-4.419	-.884	***
Constant	.042	.59	0.07	.943	-1.114	1.198	
ET	1.443	1.48	0.98	.329	-1.457	4.344	
Constant	-.67	.968	-0.69	.489	-2.566	1.227	
CON	.421	.236	1.79	.074	-.041	.883	*
Constant	-.297	.154	-1.93	.054	-.599	.005	*
Statistical Tests							
Mean dependent var	-0.271		SD dependent var		0.520		
Number of obs	9.000						

Source: Author's estimate. *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05.

Use this model to learn how Brexit will affect the British economy and how FDI will affect the economy. The FDI*Period regression coefficient is statistically significant at -0.479, suggesting a UK FDI fall following Brexit. These results bear out our premise that post-Brexit FDI has a significant impact on GDP growth. In addition, the period coefficient of -0.319 suggests that Brexit has had a significant negative effect on UK economic growth (p<0.05). Capital investment has a beneficial influence on the UK economy, with a positive coefficient of 0.531 that is statistically significant at the 10% level, offsetting the minor drag from FDI. In addition, at the 1% level, the coefficient shows that inflation slows UK economic development. Furthermore, the consumption coefficient is 0.421, which is statistically significant at the 10% level. Productivity, output, and wages all benefit from an influx of foreign direct investment. Multinational firms have increased production by adopting cutting-edge technologies and better management methods. FDI also benefits domestic economic growth and development by increasing competitiveness and fortifying supply networks. Among the United Kingdom's over a trillion dollars in FDI sources, EU nations account for more than half.

The ease and speed with which foreign investors may enter the EU Single Market is one of the many reasons why the United Kingdom is so popular. However, after Brexit, FDI may fall if trade costs rise with the EU. FDI is the practice of a foreign entity investing in a domestic enterprise. Over half of the total aggregate value of FDI in the United Kingdom is expected to come from foreign nations inside the European Union. British FDI is ranked third globally, only behind the United States and China. Countries tend to welcome FDI because it boosts their economies regarding productivity, production, and profitability. FDI helps multinational corporations expand internationally and those that do so are more likely to pay their workers more and generate bigger profits than their local competitors. It helps the economy in the long run by allowing domestic companies to learn about new technologies and methods of management from their international counterparts. Large multinational firms' supply chains are a frequent venue for the transfer of such information (Harrison & Rodriguez-Clare, 2010). FDI may also increase local firms' competitive pressure, encouraging its top executives to boost productivity. Since the vote, however, Brexit-related uncertainty has discouraged investment in the UK. Companies have either delayed their plans or decided to invest elsewhere in Europe. As companies wait for the United Kingdom to decide on trade deals, some have begun to proceed cautiously. There is a significant

favourable benefit of EU membership for FDI, with estimates ranging from 14% to 38%. The findings consistently support FDI in the UK when compared to a set of control nations.

Production, wages, and productivity increases are all possible to FDI. Increased production may be directly attributed to the superior management and cutting-edge equipment that multinational businesses often use (Xie & Yin, 2023). In addition, FDI encourages the development and growth of indigenous firms by creating competitive marketplaces and strong supply networks. Annual FDI into the United Kingdom from the European Union amounts to a whopping \$1 trillion. Foreign investors find the United Kingdom alluring because of its proximity to the European Union's single market and the ease with which it may be entered (Harrison & Rodriguez-Clare, 2010). However, following Brexit, FDI might fall as increased trade costs linked with EU trade dampen investor enthusiasm. There is a constant beneficial benefit of EU membership on FDI, with estimates ranging from 14% to 38%. The impacts are about the same whether comparing FDI flows into the UK and a group of similarly situated control nations. It is difficult to predict how a decline in FDI would affect income. Many people will be out of work if companies start moving to the continent. Trade tariffs and limitations may negatively impact investment value on access to the single market (Chairassamee & Hean, 2023) and the stock market as a whole. FDI increases productivity in the United Kingdom. British firms benefit from the innovative management techniques pioneered by multinational organizations (Bloom et al., 2012). In addition, "spillover" effects, when foreign investment benefits local enterprises in the same sector, are found by Haskel et al. (2007). Understanding the full extent of FDI's impact on national production requires considering the many ways in which FDI affects different actors in the economy. Fortunately, Alfaro et al. (2004) research might help shed light on this tricky problem by examining the effect of FDI movements on economic development in 73 nations. In nations with advanced financial markets, like the United Kingdom, the research finds that GDP rises with rising FDI levels. Brexit might cause huge adaption costs for large European companies with assets in the UK. The result will likely be a more competitive market and possibly changes to England's business environment and tax structure. FDI into England comes mostly from a few EU countries: Germany, France, Ireland, and Spain. More FDI comes from the EU into the energy industry, wholesale and retail commerce, manufacturing, and transportation than the professional and financial services sector. The United Kingdom has successfully lured FDI, along with the employment and projects that come with it. However, the choice to leave the European Union might have unintended implications elsewhere. The United Kingdom's worldwide competitiveness may decrease after Brexit, necessitating measures to enhance the business environment in other EU nations to entice multinational businesses to establish overseas headquarters elsewhere. Restoring the United Kingdom's competitiveness should be a top priority; thus, the government should look at easing environmental rules and cutting taxes, among other measures.

Our research shows that the UK economy is expanding sluggishly by 1.32% each year, with a standard deviation of 4.69%. FDI has a standard deviation of 0.29% and an average of 2.49%. Brexit has affected FDI in the UK, as the average proportion of FDI is now just 0.187%. A high inflation rate and a low average rate of return on capital investments characterize the situation in the United Kingdom. The average inflation rate ranges from 1.94% to a 5.93% peak. Exports and imports are sensitive to fluctuations in the international trade sector, accounting for between 0.604% and 0.5667% of the UK's gross domestic product. The mean value of \$83.78 and the standard deviation of \$0.946 illustrate the rising trend in total consumption prices. These results reflect the many difficulties the UK has had since Brexit, including slowed GDP growth, higher inflation, and a drop in trade percentages. These economic indices have decreased since the Brexit referendum on June 23, 2016, in which 51.9% of voters chose to leave the European Union. The governing party acknowledged the result of the referendum despite the lack of legitimacy of the process. The United Kingdom has seen a consistent reduction in FDI inflows after the EU vote, the largest decline since the data series started collecting in 2003. After the Brexit vote, there was a 16% to 20% drop in outside investment in the United Kingdom. FDI in the services sector might have been around 25% lower if the United Kingdom had stayed outside the European Union. Even while FDI in the UK has dropped, it has shown remarkable resilience in the face of increased risk aversion. However, highly trained workers in these high-value sectors face enormous risks due to Brexit's present uncertainty. This suggests that the current uncertainties have had a major effect on FDI in the UK.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This research examines how FDI affected the British economy before and after the Brexit vote. The United Kingdom can compete in global markets and deliver goods and services efficiently because of its privileged location and large pool of qualified people. However, these elements also affect the volume and composition of FDI in the UK. Critical to the country's competitiveness is its capacity to create products and services at scale to fulfill local demand without depending excessively on imports and exports from other markets. Recent growth and a rise in FDI in the UK may be traced back to the country's prominent position in the global value chain. The measures implemented after the vote will decide the economic effects of Britain's decision to leave the European Union.

Lower trade integration with the EU is predicted to have a far larger negative effect on the UK economy than the impact of lower budgetary payments, regardless of the result of Brexit discussions. According to this research, FDI in the United Kingdom has dropped significantly after the Brexit vote. The British pound will undoubtedly be affected by Brexit. We still need to find out how much of an effect uncertainty has on currency decline. Even if investing in the local currency may seem more reasonable, the currency's depreciation during high volatility hampers new investments. Investment may be less affected by Brexit if the government's macroeconomic policy decisions were more transparent. The results, however, point to the potential efficacy of a micro- or site-based strategy, based on past studies in the field, in lowering enterprise uncertainty. This situation calls for more ambitious investment plans, like the UK's incentive programmes, before joining the single market. Because EU regulations on state aid do not constrain them, UK authorities may be better positioned to provide competitive FDI incentives. It's important to emphasize, however, that the effects of such incentives are generally short-lived.

According to our results, the UK's aspirations to develop trade agreements with the EU to preserve competitiveness in recruiting foreign investment are potentially contradictory. Despite the potential advantages, others are worried that the UK's pursuit of increased tax competitiveness may damage ties with the EU. Some of Brexit's unanticipated effects would be less severe if tax rates were lowered. However, we expect a drop in FDI over the next five years, which is truly independent of the precise governance arrangements that the UK and EU decide on. Some concessions may become possible if industry-wide agreements can be reached. More investigation on this question is planned for the future. Leaving the European Union will give the UK greater leeway to make its laws. It has been argued that this would help mitigate losses from falling commerce and foreign direct investment. UK economic policy might be reshaped when the country leaves the EU, including regional development, research, agriculture, and competition and trade funding. However, other nations may impose further market constraints if the UK proposes new legislation or subsidies that do not conform to EU or WTO criteria. Due to distinct product requirements for domestic manufacturing and EU exports, regulatory divergences between the EU and the UK will drive up the cost of doing business in the UK. There will be increased hurdles for British firms to enter the EU single market if the UK does not work with the EU on policy. There are limits to this research, as there are to any. Although a quantitative technique was used, a mixed-methods approach may be more fruitful for future studies. While future research may want to consider numerous dependent variables, this one was utilized to analyze the growth of the UK economy. Time restrictions limited the sample size used in this study, although that might be increased in future studies. Future research should include mediating or moderating factors in the study. The effect of Brexit on FDI is only one of several economic outcomes that have been the subject of research. The effect of Brexit on FDI entering the United Kingdom has been the subject of both model-based and model-free research. As a result, several reforms are advocated for the United Kingdom to adopt to regain its competitive edge. Further study is required to understand how to join the EFDI in the UK fully. We used synthetic cohorts, regression analysis, and empirical models to assess the impact of FDI on trade openness. Using a regression-based technique to connect FDI and trade openness has several benefits, including accounting for FDI from all areas (not just the EU) and visualizing potential outcomes for trade impact across nations.

Ethical approval

Not Applicable.

Informed consent

The study was conducted with equal participation by all authors.

Conflicts of interests

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interests.

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Data and materials availability

All data associated with this study are present in the paper.

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